

ACCEPTABILITY AND MARKETABILITY OF POWDERED GUYABANO LEAVES AND DRIED CARROTS AS INGREDIENTS IN BISCUITS (CARROBANO BISCUITS)

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted to determine the acceptability and marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits in different proportions (5g, 10, 15g) at Sanchez Mira School of Arts and Trades and Barangay Lemu Norte, Enrile, Cagayan during the school year 2019-2020. Experimental and descriptive methods of research were used with the survey questionnaire as the main gathering instrument. The study used the Nine-Point Hedonic rating scale and Five-point Likert rating scale. The statistical tools used were weighted mean and ANOVA. A sensory evaluation was conducted with 90 respondents comprising baking students, food experts, and consumers. The 5 g proportion came as Extremely Acceptable among the three groups of respondents. Physicochemical analysis Carrobano biscuits have a moderate content of carbohydrates, moisture, protein, fiber, fat, ash, and Ph resulting in a healthier snack. For the marketability 5g and 10g were rated as Very High Potential, because the production of the materials meets the demands of market supply and consumers. There were no significant differences in the evaluation of the respondents on the acceptability of carrobano biscuits in three different proportions in terms of aroma and color, for 5g and 15g proportions, there were no significant differences except in terms of texture. There was a significant difference for the 10 g proportion in the evaluation of the respondents in terms of appearance and taste. For marketability, there were no significant differences in the evaluation of the respondents in terms of consumer demand and production cost.

Keywords: *Powdered Guyabano Leaves, Dried Carrots, Sensory evaluation, Physicochemical Analysis, Carrobano Biscuits.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, people are focusing on herbal plants especially those which are common in the environment. The use of herbal medicine is an integral part of the Philippine culture. Within this culture, various plants and vegetables have been popularly studied to determine their medicinal properties. The development of nutritious food products provides everyone with specific health benefits. Everyone wants to live a healthy lifestyle. Discovering and introducing new products with the use of herbal medicine is thus, necessary. In addition to this, the researcher wanted to investigate other native plants which could help prevent health problems. For this reason, the researcher aimed to produce a new food product from Guyabano (*Anona muricata* linn) and Carrot (*Daucus carota*).

According to Morton (2018), guyabano (*anona muricata* linn) fruit is a green, pear-shaped fruit covered with soft spines. The matured guyabano or soursop fruit weighs 2 to 5 kilograms. Guyabano fruits are ovoid and large with thin skin and soft edible whitish pulp that is fleshly and fibrous. The size ranges from 10 to 30 cm long and up to 15 centimeters width. The Guyabano fruit has a distinct sour citrus taste and sweet-sour flavor that tastes like pineapple and strawberry.

Another ingredient which was used in the study is carrots. As defined by Bjarnadottir (2019), “carrot” comes from the Greek word “Karoton”. Carrots are perhaps best known for their rich supply of the antioxidant nutrients that was actually named for them: beta-carotene and vitamin A which help to slow down the development of heart disease and plays a protective role against some diseases. Some health professionals say that one should eat dark green or deep orange fruits and vegetables at least every other day. Most of the fruits and vegetables can be eaten raw. Like carrots, this simple fruit has vitamin A which is essential for our eye, carotene and some trace minerals are found on the surface of the fruit.

However, these delicious root vegetables are the vitamin source not only of beta-carotene but also of a wide variety of antioxidants and other health-supporting nutrients. According to Banjo (2018), the areas of antioxidant benefits, cardiovascular benefits, vision health benefits, and anti-cancer benefits are the best researched areas of health research with respect to the dietary intake of carrots. In addition, carrots and guyabano leaves can kill cancer cells.

Fabiyi, et. al. (2015) stated that a lack of adequate information about the nutritional value and health benefits of carrots may not allow people to see the need of carrot intake. One needs to have knowledge of the food value of carrots to be well nourished and be in good health. Carrot contains elements that keep us healthy in many ways. Therefore, there is a need for both children and adults to consume carrots every day and the government’s awareness campaign about the usefulness of carrots will contribute immensely to people’s health. Integrating nutrition education into the curriculum of primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions will also promote healthy lifestyles and good dietary habits.

Mishra (2019) stated that biscuits are becoming a more important part of a diet. It is one of the low-cost processed foods, which is most widely consumed. Apart from the good taste, these foods with substantial energy having wholesome and nutritious quality are available at a reasonable price. It has a certain advantage, easy to use at home, even during travel, easily available in a massive variety of shapes, and appeals to all ages.

The growing consumer demand for food with nutritional and sensory quality as well as the functional claim has called for research to develop new products that include the nutritional and functional of the product, but it also considers consumer acceptance.

In this study, Guyabano and Carrots were used as ingredients in biscuits. Biscuits are derived from the Latin words *Bis* (meaning twice) and *Coctus* (cooked or baked) according to Kandam (2019). The word "Biscotti" is also a generic term for cookies in Italian. It is unleavened and has a hard and thin texture because of its low water content.

The researcher was motivated and interested to further explore and develop the combination of guyabano powder leaves and carrots in order to make natural and nutritious snacks like biscuits since adding these ingredients can turn the biscuits into a vibrant green-orange color which can be more appetizing. It can also boost the nutritional value of the biscuits as it supplies essential vitamins and minerals. In addition, this research was conducted to contribute to the growth of experimental food products that can be popularly served and appreciated on the table by locals, both children and adults, because of their nutritive value.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the acceptability and marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits (Carrobono Biscuits) in different proportions at Sanchez Mira School of Arts and Trades and Barangay Lemu Norte, Enrile, Cagayan during the school year 2019- 2020.

More specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How did the baking students, consumers, and food experts evaluate the acceptability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits with proportions of 5 grams, 10 grams, and 15 grams in terms of the following criteria?
 - 1.1. Appearance
 - 1.2. aroma
 - 1.3. taste
 - 1.4. texture
 - 1.5. Color
2. Were there significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the prepared three different sets in grams of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients of biscuits based on the given criteria?

3. What was the physicochemical analysis of Carrobano Biscuits?
 - 3.1. Carbohydrates
 - 3.2. Ph
 - 3.3. Water/ Moisture
 4. What was the level of marketability of the Carrobano Biscuits with the different proportions as perceived by the different groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1. consumer demand;
 - 4.2. supply availability; and
 - 4.3. production cost?
 5. Were there significant differences in the evaluation of the different groups of respondents on the level of marketability of guyabano powdered leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in making biscuits with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions?
 6. What were the comments and suggestions of the three groups of respondents to further improve the production of biscuits with powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots?
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METHODOLOGY

The experimental method was used in this study to determine the acceptability of produced biscuits using guyabano powdered leaves and dried carrots as ingredients to arrive at a more precise end result. According to Dragger (2018), experimental research includes manipulating a factor in under controlled conditions hence, considered as objective, systematic, and controlled investigation to predict and control phenomena and examine probability and cause among selected variables. As per variety, experimental design is a powerful design for testing hypotheses of causal relationships or effects among variables. The study also utilized a descriptive method of research, which according to Drager, always considers any data observable by the researcher. This was also used to determine the level of satisfaction of respondents with the finished product.

Sources of Data

This study was conducted in Brgy. Lemu Norte, Enrile, Cagayan, and Sanchez Mira School of Arts and Trades, Sanchez Mira, Cagayan, during the school year 2019-2020. The data of this study were obtained from 90 respondents, particularly, 30 baking students, 30 consumers, and 30 food experts.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was first sought from the Barangay captain and the school principal as well. The researcher prepared a letter addressed to the barangay captain and the school principal stating her purpose and objectives. Upon the approval of the request, a taste test was conducted. Questionnaire checklists were prepared and distributed to respondents. The finished products were subjected to sensory evaluation. The

respondents were properly oriented on what and how to evaluate the product using the questionnaire. They were also asked to taste the samples. Data on the appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture of each treatment were collected and decoded subject to statistical analysis. The researcher personally collected the questionnaires tabulated and analyzed the data and interpreted the results.

Data Gathering Instrument

A survey questionnaire checklist was used to collect data for this study. This was validated and checked by ten experts. The checklist was used to elicit evaluation from the 90 respondents on the acceptability and marketability of biscuits with powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots. It was also used to determine the degree of satisfaction in terms of the given variables likewise to gain comments and suggestions for further improvements. The 9-point Hedonic Scale was used to evaluate the acceptability of the finished product, while the Five-Point Likert scale was used to determine its marketability.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data that were gathered.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the level of acceptability and marketability of the carrobano biscuits in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, texture, and color.

9-Point Hedonic Scale		
Range	Rating Score	Descriptive Rating
8.50 - 9.00	9	Extremely Agreeable (EA)
7.50 - 8.49	8	Very Agreeable (VA)
6.50 - 7.49	7	Moderately Agreeable (MA)
5.50 - 6.49	6	Slightly Agreeable (SA)
4.50 - 5.49	5	Fairly Agreeable (FA)
3.50 - 4.49	4	Slightly Disagreeable (SD)
2.50 - 3.49	3	Moderately Disagreeable (MD)
1.50 - 2.49	2	Very Disagreeable (VD)
1.00 - 1.49	1	Extremely Disagreeable (ED)

The Five-Point Likert's scale was used to determine the marketability of the finished product.

Five-Point Likert's Scale		
Scale	Range	Verbal Description
5	4.50 – 5.00	Very High Potential (VHP)
4	3.50 – 4.49	Highly Potential (HP)

3	2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Potential (MP)
2	1.50 – 2.49	Low Potential (LP)
1	1.00 – 1.49	Very Low Potential (VLP)

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability and marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with Proportions of 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g for each of the Ingredients.

The evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of baked biscuits with proportions of 5 grams, 10 grams, and 15 grams in terms of their appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture are shown in Tables 1-9.

Table 1
Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 5 g Proportion

Criteria	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	8.43	VA	8.73	EA	8.58	EA
b. Aroma	8.75	EA	8.87	EA	8.81	EA
c. Taste	8.63	EA	8.94	EA	8.79	EA
d. Texture	8.45	VA	8.61	EA	8.50	EA
e. Color	8.68	EA	8.65	EA	8.61	EA
Grand Weighted Mean	8.59	EA	8.76	EA	8.66	EA

Note: OWM – Overall Weighted Mean

The data revealed that generally, baking students, food experts, and consumer respondents rated the biscuits as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)** as indicated by its grand weighted mean ratings of 8.59, 8.76, and 8.66, respectively.

Moreover, the food experts and consumer respondents rated all the criteria as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**. The findings imply that the three groups of respondents are particularly satisfied with the biscuit's taste and aroma.

Table 2
Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 10 g Proportion

Criteria	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	8.22	VA	8.69	EA	8.47	VA
b.						
c. Aroma	8.49	VA	8.50	EA	8.53	EA
d. Taste	8.39	VA	8.63	EA	8.49	VA
e. Texture	8.39	VA	8.57	EA	8.43	VA
f. Color	8.47	VA	8.59	EA	8.49	VA
Grand Weighted Mean	8.39	VA	8.60	EA	8.48	VA

The data in Table 2 revealed that the baking students and consumer respondents rated the biscuits as **Very Agreeable (VA)** as evidenced by its grand weighted mean ratings of 8.39 and 8.48, respectively, while the food expert respondents' evaluation was 8.60, verbally interpreted as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**.

More specifically, the baking student respondents rated all the criteria as **Very Agreeable (VA)**, while the consumer respondents rated the appearance, taste, texture, and color as **Very Agreeable (VA)** and aroma as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**.

On the other hand, the food experts rated all the criteria as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)** which means that the respondents are satisfied with the 10 g proportion.

Table 3
Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 15 g Proportion

Criteria	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	8.38	VA	8.61	EA	8.53	EA
b. Aroma	8.18	VA	8.12	VA	8.19	VA
c. Taste	8.07	VA	8.15	VA	8.11	VA
d. Texture	8.14	VA	8.56	EA	8.27	VA
e. Color	8.33	VA	8.39	VA	8.33	VA
Grand Weighted Mean	8.22	VA	8.37	VA	8.29	VA

As can be observed in Table 3, the three groups of respondents evaluated the biscuits with 15 g proportion with grand weighted mean ratings of 8.22, 8.37, and 8.29, respectively, verbally interpreted as **Very Agreeable (VA)**.

In terms of appearance, the food experts and consumer respondents agreed that it was **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**. The aroma, taste, and color were generally rated as **Very Agreeable (VA)**, while texture was evaluated as **Very Agreeable (VA)** by baking students and consumer respondents, and **Extremely Agreeable (EA)** by the food expert respondents.

These data imply that the product with 15 g proportion although acceptable, can still be further improved to meet the satisfaction of respondents.

Summary of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 5 grams, 10 grams, and 15 grams Proportion.

Table 4
Summary of the Respondents’ Evaluations of the Acceptability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 5 g, 10 g and 15 g Proportions

Proportions	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	OWM	VI	OWM
5 g	8.59	EA	8.76	EA	8.66	EA
10 g	8.39	VA	8.60	EA	8.48	VA
15 g	8.22	VA	8.37	VA	8.29	VA
Grand Weighted Mean	8.40	VA	8.58	EA	8.48	VA

Summary. Table 4 presents the summary of the overall grand weighted mean on the respondents’ evaluations on the acceptability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions.

The data revealed that the baking students and consumer respondents rated the acceptability of the biscuits as **Very Agreeable (VA)** as evidenced by the grand weighted mean ratings of 8.40 and 8.48, while the food expert respondents evaluated it with a grand weighted rating of 8.58, verbally interpreted as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**.

More specifically, the three groups of respondents rated the 5 g proportion as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**, while for the 10 g proportion, both the baking students and consumer respondents rated it as **Very Agreeable (VA)**. On the other hand, the food expert respondents rated the 10 g proportion as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**. For the 15 g proportion, the three groups of respondents rated it as **Very Agreeable (VA)**.

Table 6
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding to Aroma

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	0.22	0.11	1.58	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	5.97	0.07				
10g	Between Groups	2	0.03	0.02	0.06	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	23.50	0.27				
15g	Between Groups	2	0.09	0.05	0.08	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	52.51	0.60				

It can be observed in Table 6 that the computed F values of 1.58, 0.06 and 0.08 are smaller than the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It indicates that there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the three different proportions of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding aroma.

This implies that the three groups have similar perceptions on the biscuits with powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots in terms of aroma.

Table 7 shows the test of significant difference in the respondents' evaluations on the acceptability of powdered guyabano powdered leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions in terms of taste.

Table 7
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding to Taste

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	1.47	0.74	2.45	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	26.15	0.30				
10g	Between Groups	2	2.17	1.09	3.81	3.10	Reject the Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	87	24.83	0.29				
15g	Between Groups	2	0.11	0.06	0.08	3.10		Not Significant

	Within Groups	87	59.42	0.68			Fail to Reject the Ho	
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As clearly shown in Table 7, the computed F values of 2.45 for the 5 g proportion and 0.08 for the 15 g proportion are lower than the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. As for the 10 g proportion, the computed F value of 3.81 is greater than the critical F value, hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. It means that there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the 5 g and 15 g powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits except for the 10 g proportion.

It can be inferred that the three groups of respondents have the same impression on the 5 g and 15 g proportions except on the 10 g proportion.

Table 8 shows the test of significant difference in the respondents' evaluations on the acceptability of powdered guyabano powdered leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions in terms of aroma.

Table 8
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding to Texture

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	0.40	0.20	0.63	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	27.51	0.32				
10g	Between Groups	2	0.55	0.28	1.16	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	20.64	0.24				
15g	Between Groups	2	2.78	1.39	4.01	3.10	Reject the Ho	Significant

It can be gleaned from Table 24 that the computed F values of 0.63 for the 5 g proportion and 1.16 for the 10 g proportion are below the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. As for the 15 g proportion, the computed F value of 4.01 is greater than the critical F value, hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. It shows that there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the 5 g and 10 g powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding texture except on the 10 g proportion.

This implies that the respondents have similar views of the biscuits with 5 g and 10 g proportions because of the amount of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots in each except on the biscuits with 15 g proportions.

Table 9 shows the test of significant difference in the respondents' evaluations on the acceptability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions in terms of color.

Table 9
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding to Color

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	0.08	0.04	0.33	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	10.80	0.12				
10g	Between Groups	2	0.27	0.13	0.68	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	17.08	0.20				
15g	Between Groups	2	0.06	0.03	0.08	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	36.70	0.42				

Table 9 shows that the computed F values of 0.33, 0.68 and 0.08 are lower than the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that there is no significant difference in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the three different proportions of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding color.

This implies that the three groups of respondents agreed that the color of the biscuits with 5 g and 10 g proportion is acceptable.

Physicochemical Analysis of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Biscuits (Carrobano Biscuits)

Carbohydrates provide fuel for the central nervous system and the main source of energy for working muscles, prevent protein from being used as energy source, and enable fat metabolism. According to Smathers (2016), carbohydrates are important for brain function. It influence on "mood memory as well as a quick energy source". In fact, the recommended daily amount of carbohydrates is based on the amount of carbs the brain needs to function.

In the same view, Davidson (2018) asserts that carbohydrates are probably the most abundant and widespread organic substances in nature and essential factor of all

living things. Carbohydrate serves as the energy sources and essential structural components in organisms.

Another important and most widely used measurement in the processing and testing of foods is the determination of moisture. The amount of moisture it contains is inversely related to the amount of dry matter in foods. It has direct economic importance to the process and the consumer. Nielsen (2017) stated that food moisture analysis is important since the method used to determine moisture may lead to varying results for moisture content, depending on the form of the water present in a food. The physical, chemical aspects of food which relates with the freshness and stability for the storage of the food for a long period of time and the moisture content determine the actual quality of the food before consumption and to the subsequent processing in the food sector by the food producers.

Foods can be acidic, alkaline or neutral. The rate a food deteriorates is determined by acidity. The potential for hydrogen (pH) range is from 0 to 14, with 7.0 being neutral. A strong acid will have a pH 1, and a strong alkali will have a high pH value.

Proteins are essential for the structure, function, and regulation of the body's tissue and organs. Proteins are made up of hundreds of smaller units called amino acid that are attached to one another by peptide bonds, forming a long chain.

Table 10
Physicochemical Analysis of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits

Sample Description	Crude Protein %	Crude Fiber %	Crude Fat %	Carbohydrate %	Moisture %	Ash %	Ph %
Carrobano Biscuits	8.52	1.76	15.82	17.6	2.50	0.90	6.43

It can be gleaned from Table 10, that the product has a moderate carbohydrate content of 17.6 which means it is good for all ages. It has a moisture content of 2.50 %, which implies that the lower the amount of moisture in food the lower the risk of food spoilage. The shelf life of the food material is determined by the moisture content in the food. Low moisture foods usually slow down the growth of microorganisms, hence, the need for analysis and control of food moisture. Moisture content influences the taste, weight, appearance, and shelf life of food products. The carrobano biscuit has 8.52% protein content in each gram of biscuits, 1.76% of fiber content, 15.82% of fat, and 0.90% of ash which means that the product is good for the health of the consumers.

The pH range is from 0 to 14, water has a neutral pH level. The carrobano biscuit has a pH % of 6.43 and it is less acidic since the result of the test made is below 7.0. It should be noted that the pH range of 7.0 is neutral, above 7.0 is alkaline, and below 7.0 is considered acidic.

Level of Marketability of Carrobano Biscuits with Different Proportions as Perceived by the Respondents

The computed results on the level of marketability of carrobano biscuits with different proportions as perceived by the baking students, food experts, and consumer respondents are shown in Tables 11-17.

Table 11
Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 5 g Proportion

	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Consumer Demand	4.75	VHP	4.93	VHP	4.85	VHP
b. Supply Availability	4.42	HP	4.82	VHP	4.61	VHP
c. Production Cost	4.60	VHP	4.84	VHP	4.70	VHP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.59	VHP	4.86	VHP	4.72	VHP

The data show that in terms of the marketability of biscuits with a 5 g proportion, the three groups of respondents rated the biscuits with grand weighted mean ratings of 4.59, 4.86, and 4.72, respectively, verbally interpreted as **Very High Potential (VHP)**.

It can be observed that the food experts and consumer respondents rated all the criteria as **Very High Potential (VHP)**, while the baking students rated the supply availability as **High Potential (HP)**.

This means that in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost, the 5 g proportion has a high level of marketability.

Table 12
Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 10 g Proportion

	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Consumer Demand	4.64	VHP	4.72	VHP	4.68	VHP
b. Supply Availability	4.41	HP	4.71	VHP	4.55	VHP
c. Production Cost	4.60	VHP	4.75	VHP	4.69	VHP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.55	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.64	VHP

The table revealed that the baking students, food experts, and consumer respondents evaluated the biscuits with 10 grams as **Very High Potential (VHP)** with the ratings of 4.55, 4.73, and 4.64, respectively.

To be more specific, the food experts and consumer respondents gave the same evaluation to all criteria, while the baking students rated supply availability as **High Potential (HP)**. It implies that the product can be sold once it is offered in the market.

Table 13
Summary of the Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with 15 g Proportion

	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Consumer Demand	4.49	HP	4.55	VHP	4.51	VHP
b. Supply Availability	4.34	HP	4.71	VHP	4.49	HP
c. Production Cost	4.51	VHP	4.75	VHP	4.66	VHP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.45	HP	4.67	VHP	4.55	VHP

The data unveiled that in terms of marketability, the baking student respondents rated the biscuits with a grand weighted mean rating of 4.45, verbally interpreted as **High Potential (HP)** while the food experts and consumer respondents rated it with 4.67 and 4.55, respectively, verbally interpreted as **Very High Potential (VHP)**.

It only signifies that the carrobano biscuits with 15 g proportion can be sold in the market because of potential demand from the consumers who might be looking for affordable and nutritious snacks.

Summary. Table 14 shows the summary of the respondents' evaluation on the marketability powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits with different proportions.

Table 14
Summary of the Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits with Different Proportions

Proportions	Respondents					
	Baking Students		Food Experts		Consumers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	OWM	VI	OWM
5 Grams	4.59	VHP	4.86	VHP	4.72	VHP

10 Grams	4.55	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.64	VHP
15 Grams	4.45	HP	4.67	VHP	4.55	VHP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.53	VHP	4.75	VHP	4.64	VHP

The data show that in terms of marketability, the three groups of respondents rated the biscuits with different proportions with the grand weighted mean ratings of 4.53, 4.75, and 4.64, respectively, verbally interpreted as **Very High Potential (VHP)**.

It is presumed that the three groups of respondents believe that the 5 g proportion has the highest level of marketability. This may be due to its aroma, taste, and color which the respondents rated as **Extremely Agreeable (EA)**. A glance at Table 14 also shows that the 5 g proportion has the highest overall weighted mean ratings.

Test of Significant Differences in the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Making Biscuits with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g Proportions

The test of significant difference in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of guyabano powdered leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportion in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost.

Table 15 shows the analysis of variance of respondents' evaluation on the marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding consumer demand.

Table 15
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding Consumer Demand

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	0.49	0.25	2.77	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	7.71	0.09				
10g	Between Groups	2	0.10	0.05	0.28	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	14.85	0.17				
15g	Between Groups	2	0.06	0.03	0.11	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	22.43	0.26				

Table 15 shows that the computed F values of 2.77, 0.28, and 0.11 are less than the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions as ingredients in biscuits as to consumer demand.

This means that the three groups of respondents agree that the biscuits' level of marketability is high in terms of consumer demand.

Table 16 shows the analysis of variance of respondents' evaluation on the marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding supply availability.

Table 16
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding Supply Availability

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	2.40	1.20	9.55	3.10	Reject the Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	87	10.93	0.13				
10g	Between Groups	2	1.47	0.74	3.23	3.10	Reject the Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	87	19.85	0.23				
15g	Between Groups	2	2.03	1.02	3.53	3.10	Reject the Ho	Significant
	Within Groups	87	25.09	0.29				

As revealed in Table 16, the computed F values of 9.55, 3.23 and 3.53 are higher than the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. It shows that there are significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions as ingredients in biscuits.

This could mean that the three groups of respondents have different views on the level of marketability of the carrobano biscuits in terms of supply availability.

Table 17 shows the analysis of variance of respondents' evaluation on the marketability of powdered guybano leaves and dried carrots as ingredients in biscuits regarding production cost.

Table 17
Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability of Powdered Guyabano Leaves and Dried Carrots as Ingredients in Biscuits Regarding Production Cost

P	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	$F_{\text{computed Value}}$	$F_{\text{critical Value}} (\alpha=5\%)$	Decision	Interpretation
5g	Between Groups	2	0.87	0.44	2.83	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	13.39	0.15				
10g	Between Groups	2	0.33	0.16	1.59	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	8.93	0.10				
15g	Between Groups	2	0.88	0.44	2.77	3.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87	13.80	0.16				

It can be viewed in Table 17 that the computed F values of 2.83, 1.59 and 2.77 are below the critical F value of 3.10. At the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the marketability of powdered guyabano leaves and dried carrots with 5 g, 10 g, and 15 g proportions as ingredients in biscuits as to production cost.

The data gathered showed that all three groups of respondents had similar evaluations of the products' marketability in terms of production cost.

Conclusions

1. The carrobano biscuits with a 5 g proportion is the most acceptable proportion in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, texture, and color as compared to other proportions.
2. There were no significant differences in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of carrobano biscuits in three different proportions in terms of aroma and color. As for the 5 g and 15 g proportions, there were no significant differences in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents except in terms of texture. For the 10 g proportion, there was a significant difference in the evaluation of the respondents in terms of appearance and taste.
3. In terms of physicochemical analysis, the carrobano biscuits have a lesser risk of food spoilage and bacterial growth; it has a high carbohydrate content and moderate protein content which is essential for the structure, function, and regulation of tissues and organs of the body.

4. The carrobano biscuits with 5 g and 10 g proportions have a higher potential in the market as compared to the 15 g proportion.
5. There were no significant differences in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of carrobano biscuits in terms of consumer demand and production cost except in terms of supply availability.
6. The comments and suggestions of the three groups of respondents to further improve the product were as follows:

Comments:

- The carrobano biscuits taste very good especially the 5 g proportion as compared to the other proportions.
- The appearance, aroma, and color of the product are unique and it has a delicate smell.
- The ingredients are locally available and affordable.
- The carrobano biscuits are good because it is a nutritious snack.

Suggestions:

- Add more carrots to improve the green-orange color of the biscuits.
 - Balance the taste of carrobano biscuits with a 15 g proportion so it will not overpower the other ingredients.
 - The aroma of the carrobano biscuits could be improved by adding vanilla extract to lessen the smell of the guyabano powdered leaves in 15 g proportion.
 - Other researchers should consider promoting carrobano biscuits as one of the baked products in the market.
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Recommendations

1. The students, through the researcher, should craft a project proposal on the production of biscuits for possible research grants from the Department of Science and Technology and the Department of Agriculture.
 2. The local government should promote the carrobano biscuits as one of the baked products in the local market.
 3. Other researchers may undertake studies on different baked products utilizing other healthy ingredients.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

All respondents provided their informed consent after being properly informed about the nature and purpose of the study. Participants were made fully aware that they might leave the study at any time without facing any consequences. The respondents' identities were securely kept anonymous, and their welfare was protected at every stage of the study. The conduct of this study has not revealed any conflicts of interest, according to the authors. Strict precautions were taken to prevent plagiarism and to make sure that all contributions and sources were properly acknowledged. In addition, the data were

interpreted without bias and were only utilized for study, in accordance with the strictest ethical guidelines.

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